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HUDUDLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH XUSUSIYATLARI

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В РАЗВИТИИ РЕГИОНОВ

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi, raqamli iqtisodiyotga xos bo'lgan texnologik o'zgarishlar, mamlakatda ushbu sohani rivojlantirishdagi islohotlar, YaIMdagi o'zgarishlar, mintaqalarda raqamlashtirish sohasidagi o'zgarishlar yoritilgan bo'lib, muallif amaliy tavsiyalar beradi.

ANNOTATION

This article covers the concept of digital economy, technological changes inherent in the digital economy, reforms in the development of this sector in the country, changes in GDP, changes in the field of digitalization in the regions, the author puts forward practical recommendations.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается концепция цифровой экономики, технологические изменения, присущие цифровой экономике, реформы в развитии этого сектора в стране, изменения в ВВП, изменения в сфере цифровизации в регионах, автор выдвигает практические рекомендации.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

raqamlashtirish, raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, samaradorlik, virtual muhit, IT-park, dasturiy mahsulotlar, texnologik inqilob.

KEYWORDS

digitalization, development of the digital economy, efficiency, virtual environment, IT park, software products, technological revolution.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

цифровизация, развитие цифровой экономики, эффективность, виртуальная среда, IT-парк, программные продукты, технологическая революция

INTRODUCTION

Management of the socio-economic development and future development of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of science, scientific, social and humanitarian technologies, digital economy. This system is characterized by the rapid development of digital technologies, the revolution in the information sector and the acceleration of the globalization processes of the economy. To implement reforms in this area, on April 8, 2020, a decision was made "on measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government." At the same time, the decision also clearly outlined the financial resources of new projects. Within the framework of "e-government", 104 projects worth 1.3 trillion, 87 projects worth 5.3 trillion in the real sector of the economy, 35 projects worth 15.1 trillion in telecommunications, 24 projects in the agrarian sector, 18 IT parks.

In this regard, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that "if we do not fully implement these works in the next 2-3 years, each of our late years will bring our country back 10 years." [1]

MAIN PART

Focusing on the organizational and economic conditions created in our country in this regard, in 2017-2021 a special definition of the issue of digital economy was made in the tasks set out in the state program on the implementation of the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the year of Science, Education and development of Like the developed countries of the world, the transition to a digital economy continues in our country in rapid pictures. In particular, 2020 will be declared the "year of development of Science, Education and digital economy" by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the transition to digital economy is defined as one of Uzbekistan's priorities for the next 5 years. On January 24, 2020, in his address to the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the announcement of the current year as the "year of development of Science, Education and digital

economy" opens up wide prospects for digitization. Digitization of the economy provides an opportunity to expand the capabilities of the country's economy, quickly and cheaply solve social, economic, political and environmental problems in it. It is through the digitization of the economy that, covering all the existing platforms in society, affects the indicators of efficiency, the value added being created in the economy, the employment problem, the level of profitability, cost optimization and the acceleration of trade sales.

"Digital economy is an economic Internet activity, as well as forms, methods, tools and the communication environment of its implementation" [1, 402]. "Digitization is a paradigm shift in our way of thinking, our movement, our environment and our communication with each other" i.e., digitization is a change in the paradigm of communication and interaction [2]. Digital economy is a virtual environment in which the production complex creates products and services that provide facilities for humans, and an economic production system using digital technologies. Also, digital economy can cover everything that can be formalized, that is, manifested in logical schemes. Life itself provides an opportunity to transform these "things" into a system of production, distribution, exchange, and consumption.

From the above definitions, it should be noted that the digital economy is a virtual environment in which the production complex creates products and services that provide facilities for humans, and an economic production system using digital technologies. Also, digital economy can cover everything that can be formalized, that is, manifested in logical schemes. The effectiveness of their use has been transformed into increasing knowledge, and socio-economic ties are becoming more and more extensive.

The main factor of digital transformations in the activities of market entities is the development of Digital Culture.

Digital economy allows you to overcome the limitations inherent in classical economics due

to the presence of certain features of a unique function:

1. Several people cannot use material products, since digital products have no such barriers: they can be copied and distributed among an unlimited circle of people.

2. It is forbidden to use materials during use. Digital products do not lose their original properties, and these properties can also be improved in the process of working together or exchanging.

3. Information and communication areas prevent restrictions on the size of the areas available in typical commercial premises, and at the same time in terms of the number and quantity of customers served at the same time [3,4.]

On the basis of the study of the socio-economic development of the Jizzakh region, selected as the object of research, investiture in this region is one of the most important tasks in the present day, increasing attractiveness, increasing innovation activity, development of production and social infrastructure, minimizing territorial imbalance in the field of socio-economic development, strengthening interregional relations.

At the same time, the volume of gross regional product in the Jizzakh region in January–June 2021 amounted to 8,877.2 billion at current prices. sum and grew by 4.9% compared to the January-June 2020yil result. The YAHM deflator index is 115.6% from January-June 2020. The contribution of Jizzakh region to the formation of GDP in the Republic of Uzbekistan reached 2.8%. The GDP per capita is 6,261.7 thousand rubles, which is 2.8% higher than in the corresponding period of last year. The Gross Value Added created in all sectors of the region's economy was 97.2% of total GDP, while net taxes on products were 2.8% [4].

In addition, one of the distinctive features of the formation and implementation of the digital economy is the implementation of regional policies. In the field of regional development, it is necessary to carry out the following strategic tasks: to increase the competitiveness of the regions as a socio-economic system and strengthen their

resource potential, develop human capital, create institutional conditions, effectively manage processes and provide software for monitoring financial and economic security at the level of a business entity online in order to.

Today we will put forward the following suggestions and recommendations so that enterprises and organizations can achieve convenience in the results of applying it technologies to their work:

- dissemination and implementation of ideas for the development of a competitive economy;

- high chances of selecting competitive professionals;

- achieve remote operation of the information products market between consumers, manufacturers, intermediaries;

- provide more quality services with the help of highly qualified specialists who work directly in close communication;

- improve information and communication systems, create a database of investment projects and opportunities under implementation;

- strengthening the dominance of the information industry, achieving the development of the industry of production and services on an increasingly knowledge-based and innovation basis.

CONCLUSION

In general, today digital technologies are an integral part of the social, political and cultural life of all subjects of the world economic system and the basis of Social Development. Uzbekistan, like most countries of the world, is on the verge of another technological revolution, the emergence of a new civilization, characterized by an important role of knowledge, science, technology and information in all spheres of life. After all, in the current complex period, it is very important for Uzbekistan to turn the traditional economy into a modern information, intellectual, digital economy as much as possible.

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